

A STUDY ON THE DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE OF GRP BOX BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

By means of the investigation and practice both of China and other countries and of the author's own research experience, the present paper attempts to make an initial study of the structural characteristics, calculation, design and manufacture process of GRP box beams.

Keywords: GRP box beam, structural characteristics, design, calculation, manufacture.

1. INTRODUCTION

GRP box beam is a kind of reasonable and effective structural form in the use of GRP in heavy long-span structures. This which combines the advantages of both the GRP materials and the box beam structures and composes a new type of structure, which most effectively makes use of the double designability of GRP material's properties and the box beam's section parameters, compensates the box beam's geometrical stiffness for the material's physical stiffness shortages in order to improve and promote the structure's comprehensive and overall stiffness; and the structure may be adapted to the stress state which exists in different parts of the box-beams' cross-section by choosing the element materials and layer lay-up design. And thus the GRP plays a more effective role especially by taking advantage of its lightness, high strength, resisting fatigue and striking, resisting corrosion, and being easily formed so as to raise the effective bearing capacity of the box beam structures and the capacity of its ultimate span and the ability of its economic competition.

The research and practical use of the GRP box beam indicates that the key point of success of the structure being in the long-span and carrying heavy force are as follows: (1) the theory by which is used for calculation and the process by which is used for designing should be correct; (2) the manufacture process should be able to translate design purpose into reality; (3) the design and manufacturing should be simple, convenient and inexpensive^[1]. In trying to make the GRP box beam more effective use in the heavy long-span structures the present paper, by introducing both the world-wide researches and the author's own study and practice, purports to make an initial study of the design and manufacture as well as related issues, and thus to find out the characteristics and principles of this new type of structures and to explore more complete design and calculation theory and reliable manufacturing process, especially the simplified design and calculation methodology that efficiently helps the projects and fast-speed construction techniques in large structures' manufacture.

2. THE STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GRP BOX BEAMS

GRP box beams have similarities as well as quite a lot of differences structurally compared

with traditional material box beam. The chief characteristics and the parameters from which they receive the influences are generally as follows:

2. 1. The Structure Characteristics Received the Double Influence of the Material Property and the Cross—Section Parameter

The optimizational design of the component materials, material layer and direction and the parameter of the cross—section of the GRP box beam may be able to make the stiffness in bending and twisting unity area of the section of the box beam the largest. Similar to that of the traditional material box beams, the "economic stiffness" is chiefly promoted by enlarging the box beam's geometrical dimension. What differs is that the steadiness of the box beam depends more still upon the material and material direction of the beam. For example, the compression flange of the GRP box beam, whose longitudinal compress—buckling critical stress is as follows^[2]:

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 \delta^2}{3(1 - \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL})b^2} (\sqrt{E_L E_T} + \frac{E_L \nu_{TL} + E_T \nu_{LT}}{2} + G) \quad (1)$$

This stress mainly rests on the value and distribution of longitudinal transvers modulus of elasticity of the flange and takes $\sqrt{E_L E_T}$ as index of evaluation. The comparison of two kinds of beams in the same of cross—section size and component material cited in the reference [2] indicates that it's rather better to have a structure which be simultaneously strengthened by longitudinal and transversal fibers of the same volum content since we would get a lower E_T even though obtained a bigger E_L if merely strenthening by longitudinal fabers;

Beam B1: Compression flange ply: (0)₆;

$$E_L = 17.81 Gpa, \quad E_T = 4.95 Gpa, \quad \sqrt{E_L E_T} = 9.39 Gpa, \quad \sigma_{cr} = 79.2 Mpa;$$

Beam B5: Compression flange ply: (0°/90°)₆;

$$E_L = 13.45 Gpa, \quad E_T = 13.45 Gpa, \quad \sqrt{E_L E_T} = 13.45 Gpa, \quad \sigma_{cr} = 99.7 Mpa.$$

2. 2. The Existence of Crossing Effect and Coupling Effect

The reasonable design of the GRP box beams should make the thickness of the compression flange greater than that of the tension flange^{[2],[3]}. This, however, has led to the result that the section neutral—axis is not on the central line at the beam height and thus brought the coupling effect. In addition to these, together with the crossing effect that is brought from the influence of the material anisotropy, it has made the stress, the deformation and its distribution somewhat complicated. Moreover, to a greater degree, it differs from the box beams made from traditional materials. For example, when the beam bends, its stress changes not only in height but also in width of the beam and the difference of the normal stress around the symmetrical corner of cross—section may be as great as 20%^{[4],[5]}. Again, the sectional shear form coefficient of the GRP box beam can merely be stated as in a general formula;

$$f_s = \frac{GA}{EI^2} \int \frac{\overline{ES}^2}{G_K b_K^2} dA \quad (2)$$

not as a general result;

$$f_s = A/A_0 \quad (A, \text{area of the beam cross—section}, A_0, \text{area of web cross—section}) \quad (3)$$

It is these two sorts of pheonomena that it is possible to give a reasonable account for the difference between the theoretical values and experimental results of the stress and the deflection indicated in reference [6],[7].

2. 3. The Specialness of The Behaviour under Long Term Loading

The behaviour of the GRP box beams under long term loading is quite special. A experimental study of three GRP laminated box beam (length, 6m; height, 300mm; width, 150mm) for two years in reference [2] turned out as the following conclusions;

(a) Initial deflections under approximately one—third ultimate load increased by 110% over

a period of about two years. The majority (three-quarters) of this creep deflection occurred in the first 1000h.

(b) Tensile strain in the tension flange at mid-span also increased by about 110% over a period of two years. About half of this tensile creep occurred in the first 4000 h.

(c) Compressive creep strains increased up to 8000 h and then decreased for the remainder of the two-year period. This is due to the modulus of elasticity of the compression flange material decreasing with time, resulting in the onset of compression buckling.

(d) Shearing strains over the two-year period increased by about 150%. About half of this increase occurred in the first 4000 h. The rate of shear creep declined towards the latter part of the two-year period due to the onset of buckling.

(e) The experimental results for the beam subjected to a load-unload cycle for three months before being continuously loaded are shown that the great majority of the creep strain or deflection was recovered during the unloading cycle.

References [6], [7], [8] are also proved to be the conclusion (e) by means of experimental studies. This, to actual project structures, is especially important. For example, GRP box beams used as bridge structures, do not always carry goods or people the whole day. Moreover, the dead load of box beams is smaller than that of the traditional material beams and the deflection caused by it may die away by means of prebending. Therefore, much less influence is exerted upon the GRP box beams under long term loading.

2. 4. Fine Behaviour under Dynamic and Fatigue Loading

Because of the nature of the GRP box beams partial materials, intercontaction with others and the effectiveness of the sectional shape, the lessening of the wave motion and wiping of the vibration becomes possible and thus degraded the dynamic effect. Besides, its self-vibration frequency is about similar to the C30 concrete beam while its dynamic damage is much slighter than that of the latter. In addition, GRP box beam is more capable of resisting fatigue than traditional material box beams because the fiber itself is able to lessen the extent of the spreading of the cracks and to rearrange the inner forces. EMPA has had two FRP-box beams (length: 3 m; height: 188 mm; width: 118 mm) tested under fatigue loading, the test was controlled by sinusoidal load at a frequency of 2 Hz, the beam tested at 19.1% of the failure load did not develop any detectable damage before the test was terminated at 10^8 cycles (1.59 years of loading), the bending stiffness of this beam after 10^8 cycles was identical to that before testing. The beam tested at 28.6% of the failure load showed no damage for the first 4×10^6 cycles; at this point matrix cracks initiated on the matrix-rich surface of the beam on the tensile side. Even at 10^8 cycles, the observed damage caused a decrease in bending stiffness of only 2%^[9].

Because of its fine behaviour under dynamic and fatigue loading, GRP box beams can be employed advantageously in heavy long-span structure construction.

2. 5. Good Heat Steadiness

The heat behaviour of GRP chiefly rests on the heat behaviour of the resin in which it exists. But within the limited temperature of the resin, the GRP box beams made of sandwich plates have a quite steady heat behaviour after they are protected by means of adding color to resist ultraviolet ray radiation and related construction process. The experimental study in reference [7] indicates that the temperature of the box beams change with the place which receives sunshine and the sunshine. The sunny exposure raised about 50% compared with the temperature of the atmosphere while the shady spot and the inside of the box do not have much difference in temperature. Above all, the heat stress of this GRP box beam is far less greater than that of the traditional material box beams and the time it cost is similarly far less longer than that of the traditional ones because very little heat comes into the inside of the box, and meanwhile the surface heat rapidly dies away with the transference of the sunshining spot (about 6 h decrease to the air temperature) and the heat creep effect is completely to recover within the limit temperature of the resin. Hence GRP box beam made of

sandwich plate is a reasonable and effective structure to raise up the heat steadiness of GRP structures.

3. DESIGN AND CALCULATION OF GRP BOX BEAMS

3.1. Calculation Analysis of GRP Box Beams

3.1.1. Analytical Theory

GRP box beam is a special thin-walled bar structure that which is anisotropic in materials and which different in thickness and layer of each thin-section. The mechanical analytical calculation reflecting this special structure is quite complicated. At present, only some of the special ply analysis can have probable analytical result. Consulting with reference [4], as to single-box single-room GRP box beams made of laminates which only include $0^\circ, 90^\circ, \pm\alpha$ (taken as one lamina), the mechanical parameters under short term loading may be counted according to the following formuluss:

Basic Equations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \overline{EA} \frac{d^2u}{dx^2} &= -q_x \\ \overline{EI}_y \frac{d^4w}{dx^4} &= q_x + \frac{dm_y}{dx} \\ \overline{EI}_x \frac{d^4v}{dx^4} &= q_y + \frac{dm_x}{dx} \\ \overline{GI}_\rho \frac{d^2\theta}{dx^2} - (\overline{GI}_\rho - \overline{GI}_0) \frac{d^2\beta}{dx^2} &= -m_x \\ \overline{EI}_w \frac{d^2\beta}{dx^2} - (\overline{GI}_\rho - \overline{GI}_0) \frac{d^2\beta}{dx^2} + (\overline{GI}_\rho - \overline{GI}_0) \frac{d^2\theta}{dx^2} &= \frac{db}{dx} \\ \frac{d\beta}{dx} &= \frac{d\theta}{dx} + \frac{\overline{EI}_w}{(\overline{GI}_\rho - \overline{GI}_0)^2} (\overline{GI}_\rho \frac{d^3\theta}{dx^3} + \frac{dm_x}{dx}) - \frac{b}{(\overline{GI}_\rho - \overline{GI}_0)} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

Boundary Conditions:

when $x=0$, or L ,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} N &= \overline{N}, \quad M_y = \overline{M}_y, \quad Q_x = \overline{Q}_x, \quad M_x = \overline{M}_x, \quad Q_y = \overline{Q}_y, \quad M_z = \overline{M}_z, \quad B = \overline{B} \\ \text{or } u &= \overline{u}, \quad \frac{dw}{dx} = \frac{d\overline{w}}{dx}, \quad w = \overline{w}, \quad \frac{dv}{dx} = \frac{d\overline{v}}{dx}, \quad v = \overline{v}, \quad \theta = \overline{\theta}, \quad \frac{d\beta}{dx} = \frac{d\overline{\beta}}{dx} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

Physical Equations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} N &= \overline{EA} \frac{du}{dx}, \quad M_y = -\overline{EI}_y \frac{d^2w}{dx^2}, \quad Q_x = -\overline{EI}_y \frac{d^3w}{dx^3} + m_y \\ M_x &= -\overline{EI}_x \frac{d^2v}{dx^2}, \quad Q_y = -\overline{EI}_x \frac{d^3v}{dx^3} + m_x, \quad M_z = \overline{GI}_\rho \frac{d\theta}{dx} - (\overline{GI}_\rho - \overline{GI}_0) \frac{d\beta}{dx} \\ B &= -\overline{EI}_w \frac{d^2\beta}{dx^2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Geometrical Equations:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \epsilon_x &= \frac{du}{dx} - \frac{d^2v}{dx^2}y - \frac{d^2w}{dx^2}z - \frac{d^2\beta}{dx^2}\omega_A^* \\ \gamma_{xz} &= \frac{d\theta}{dx}h_A - \frac{d\beta}{dx}(h_A - e) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

Stress Formula:

$$\sigma_x = E\epsilon_x, \quad \tau_{xz} = G\gamma_{xz} \quad (8)$$

Parameter Relations:

$$E = \overline{Q}_{11} - \frac{\overline{Q}_{12}^2}{\overline{Q}_{22}}, \quad G = \overline{Q}_{66} - \frac{\overline{Q}_{26}^2}{\overline{Q}_{22}} \quad (9)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{Q}_{11} &= Q_{11}\cos^4\alpha + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha + Q_{22}\sin^4\alpha \\ \bar{Q}_{12} &= Q_{12} + (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66})\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha \\ \bar{Q}_{22} &= Q_{22}\cos^4\alpha + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha + Q_{11}\sin^4\alpha \\ \bar{Q}_{66} &= Q_{66} + (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66})\sin^2\alpha\cos^2\alpha \\ \bar{Q}_{16} &= (Q_{11} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\sin\alpha\cos^3\alpha - (Q_{22} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\sin^3\alpha\cos\alpha \\ \bar{Q}_{26} &= (Q_{11} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\sin^3\alpha\cos\alpha - (Q_{22} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66})\sin\alpha\cos^3\alpha \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= \frac{E_L}{1 - \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL}}, & Q_{12} &= \frac{E_L\nu_{TL}}{1 - \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL}} = \frac{E_T\nu_{LT}}{1 - \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL}} \\ Q_{22} &= \frac{E_T}{1 - \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL}}, & Q_{66} &= G_{LT} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (11)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{E}A &= \oint_{\delta} E dtds, & \bar{E}I_y &= \oint_{\delta} Ez^2 dtds, & \bar{E}I_x &= \oint_{\delta} Ey^2 dtds, \\ \bar{G}I_{\rho} &= \oint_{\delta} Gh_A^2 dtds, & \bar{G}I_0 &= \frac{\Omega^2}{\oint \frac{ds}{G\delta}}, & \bar{E}I_w &= \oint_{\delta} E(\omega_A^*)^2 dtds \\ \bar{G}\delta &= \int_{\delta} G dt, & \Omega &= \oint h_A ds = 2bh \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (12)$$

$$\omega_A^*(s) = \omega_A(s) - \int_{p_0}^p e(s) ds, \quad \omega_A(s) = \int_{p_0}^p h_A ds, \quad e(s) = \frac{\Omega}{\bar{G}\delta} \oint \frac{ds}{\bar{G}\delta} \quad (13)$$

Where, $q_x, q_y, q_z, m_x, m_y, m_z$, represent the forces and moment loadings applying on a unit of length of a beam composed of the component of forces on the surface of the box beams, here they are p_x, p_y, p_z ; b represents the double moment caused by p_x ; u, v, w , are displacement in the direction of x, y, z axis; α is the angle between the fiber main direction (the direction L) of calculated lamina and the Longitudinal axis (x axis) of the beam. The relation between sectional parameters is indicated as in Figure 1. And the determination of the main inertia axis y, z and the twisting center A and fan coordinate ω_A^* and its origin p_0 are in the reference [4]

Figure 1

3. 1. 2. The Simplified Method of Calculation

Structural experiments and certain construction practice indicate that about the GRP box beams meeting the case of thin-wall bar dimension, the thin-section of the beams mainly undergoes thin-film forces^{[10],[11],[12]}. Therefore, inner forces in the beams may be simplified into the thin-film forces independently exerted on the roof, bottom and the side of the box beams and be calculated approximately. For instance, as far as the sectional form of the laminated GRP box beams as indicated in Figure 2 is concerned, when the beam bends, the bending moment M in the beam is approximately regarded as composition of the longitudinal thin-film force in the compression flange and tension flange of the beam, the shear force in the beam is from the transversal thin-film force provided by the side and thus the stress in the cross-section may be calculated as the following:

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 \sigma_1 &= \frac{\overline{EA_1}h_1}{A_1(EA_1h_1^2 + EA_2h_2^2)}M \\
 \sigma_2 &= \frac{\overline{EA_2}h_2}{A_2(EA_1h_1^2 + EA_2h_2^2)}M \\
 \tau_{3max} &= \frac{f_1 b_1}{A_3(b_1 + b_2)}Q \\
 \tau_{4max} &= \frac{f_2 b_2}{A_4(b_1 + b_2)}Q
 \end{aligned} \right\} (14)$$

Figure 2

Where,

σ_1, σ_2 = the average normal stress in the compression flange and tension flange of the box beam;

τ_{3max}, τ_{4max} = the maximum shear stress on the left and right web of the box beam;

$\overline{EA_1}, \overline{EA_2}$ = compressive stiffness of the compressive and tensile flange of the box beam;

f_i = shearing form parameter of the box beam, determined by Formula (2) or (3).

Formula (14) is much simplified than the analytical formulas (4)~(13), hence it is more suitable to be used in projects especially when initially designed it can be noted that the above formula is both quick, simple and safe in determining the wall's thickness and the limitation of the box beam.

3.2. The Main Points on the Design of the GRP Box Beams

3.2.1. The Design Criterion

The design on the loading capacity of GRP box beams may be calculated according to allowable stress process, in which design be to controlled the stress in the beam to less than allowable stress and so the design criterion may be shown as the following:

$$\sigma_{max} \leq [\sigma] = \frac{\sigma_b}{k} \quad (15)$$

where, σ_b represents the loading capacity limitation calculated the lamina of the box beam, it is selected according to the loading effects of the beams, its employed requirements and the failure strength σ_f or its deflection limitation (e. g. restraining $\epsilon \leq 0.3\%$), steadiness limitation and the resonance limitation corresponding material strength σ_r . And k stands for the safety factor of loading capacity of the beam, when the beam is calculated according to the static behaviour by means of "replacement design", it is advisable to impart values according to the following table 1^{[2],[13],[14]}; When calculated according to orthotropic theory, and considering of strength limits various kinds, it can be determined of the values as following table 2^{[13],[15]}.

Table 1 The Safety Factor of Loading Capacity of the GRP Box Beam by Means of "Replacement Design"

Static Loading		Dynamic Loading				Wet-thermal Effecting	
short-term	long-term	repeted	alternating	vibrating	striking	short-term	long-term
2	4	6	6	10	10	1.4	2.8

Notice that the design criterion [15] only applies to the state of single axis stress at the point of design control of the beam's section, as to the multi-axis state the strength limitation caused by combined stress and multi-axis strength theory should be taken into consideration. For example, the design of the flanges of the box beams subjected to bend and shear loading should have a criterion as the following^[12]:

$$\frac{\sigma_{xz}}{\sigma_{(cr)}} + \left(\frac{\tau_{xzy}}{\tau_{(cr)}} \right)^2 \leq 1 \quad (16)$$

Where,

$$\sigma_{cx}^{(cr)} \approx \frac{\pi^2 t_c^2 E}{12b^2(1 - \nu_{cx}\nu_{cyx})} \left(\frac{a}{b} + \frac{b}{a}\right)^2; \quad \tau_{(cxy)}^{(cr)} \approx \frac{7\pi^2 t_c^2 E}{12b(1 - \nu_{cx}\nu_{cyx})}, \quad (1 \approx \frac{a}{b} \approx 2)$$

$$E = \sqrt[3]{4E_{cx}E_{cy}G_{cxy}}$$

Where, the geometrical parameter a, b, t are the box length (x direction), width (y direction) and thinness (z direction) calculated flange among the two transversal partitions inside beam, the physical parameter are E_{cx}, E_{cy}, G_{cxy} , which are the compressive modulus of elasticity and inside plane shearing modulus in the direction of x and y .

The design of the stiffness of GRP box beams, it is advisable to determine the rapid elastic

Table 2 The Safety Factor of Loading Capacity of GRP Box Beams Calculated According to the Orthopic Theory

Compressive Safety Factor k		$k = k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n$
Classified Safety Factor	Basic Safety Factor k_0	$\sigma_s = \sigma_t, \quad k_0 = 1.3$
		$\sigma_s = \sigma_c, \quad k_0 = 1.2$
	Factor of Material Reliability k_1	Reckon the value of the material behaviour under atmospheric temperature and short-term static Loading experiment, $k_1 = 1.1$
		In reference to ready results Reckon the designed maerial behaviour, $k_1 = 1.2$
	Factor of Structural uses and Importance k_2	Case caused injury and death, $k_2 = 1.2$
		Greater influence on public and society, $k_2 = 1.1$
		General case, $k_2 = 1.0$
		Makeshift equipment, $k_2 = 0.9$
	Factor of Calculated Load Deviation k_3	Dead load, $k_3 = 1.0 \sim 1.2$
		Live load, $k_3 = 1.0 \sim 1.4$
	Factor of Structural Calculation Exactness k_4	Calculation by finite element method and check by test, $k_4 = 1.0$
		Simplified calculation, $k_4 = 1.15$
Calculation in the means of isotropy theory, $k_4 = 1.3$		
Factor of Material Property Dispersity k_5	Make samples and experimets according to actual construction, $k_5 = 1/[1 - k_p(\sigma/\bar{x})]$	
	Consideration of process influnces instead of actual experiences, $k_5 = 1.2 \sim 1.5$	
Dynamic Loading Effect k_6	$k_6 = 1.2$	

* \bar{x} = average value of material properties, σ = standard deviation of material properties, $k_p = 3.09$ (corresponding to reliability 99.9%)

displacement reacted by the short-term static loading and then multiply the displacement enlarging parameter under the effect of the long-term static loading, dynamic loading and the effect of heat and wetness, restrain it less than the allowable displacement and the design criterion is

$$k\delta_{j,\dots} \leq [\delta] \quad (17)$$

Quite little research into the value of k and the following is only a reference^{[2],[8],[14],[15],[16]};

long-term static loading effects: $k=k_1=2\sim 4$;
 heat-wet effects: $k=k_2=1.4\sim 2.8$;
 dynamic loading effects: $k=k_3=2.6\sim 5.2$;
 comprehensive effects: plus each displacement considered above effect.

3.2.2. Main Point for Design

- (a) The design of the GRP beam is controlled in the condition of stiffness and the steadiness.
 (b) In designing of stiffness the shearing deflection of the beam is not to be neglected [5].
 (c) Make $b/h=(1/2)\sim 1$ as possible as it can be so as to reduce the additional normal stress caused by shearing deflection, otherwise the normal stress around the corner of the beam will possibly increase.
 (d) In order to have each part of the box beams simultaneously get in the state of ultimate bearing capacity, it is advisable to determine the compression flange's thickness 1.5 times the tension flange and meanwhile try to avoid using the single fiber reinforced layer construction to raise the compressive buckling critical stress; the side, the web of the beam makes use of $\pm 45^\circ$ and $\pm 60^\circ$ mixture layer so as to have a fine comprehensive behaviour of resisting compressive and shearing buckling; reinforce the bottom flange near to the bearing and the end partitions of the beam to protect the shearing damage of the bottom flange, the webs and the end partitions from outwards cracking.
 (e) In order to reinforce the total stiffness and the partial resisting stiffness of the box beams it is advisable to construct a steel-net/SMC hybrid poly laminate or concrete plate to form a sort of multiple material composite beam and to have as a result that the composite advantage of this multi-material structure.

4. MANUFACTURE PROCESS OF GRP BOX BEAMS

GRP box beams are a kind of large-scaled special-shape structure and thus are difficult to be formed mechanically. Generally they formed by hand lay-up. The quality of the manufactured beams very much relies on the skillfulness, the consciousness and the craftsmanship (process) of the manufacturers. Taking the fore GRP bridges in Chongqing (Sichuan, China) for instance, the qualities between extends to 80% by different factories. This tells that the properties of the GRP beam to a larger degree depends upon the effect of manufacture. Hence it is more profitable to enhance the manufacture process so as to promote the characteristics of the structures.

During the study of the manufacturing process of GRP box beams the most characteristic is the box beams made of sandwich constructions. We have as a result the following ideas after a series of study and practice.

GRP box beams made of sandwich constructions are before hand lay-up in the negative mould; Firstly laying-up the external covers of the flanges and webs to form laminated opening box beam. Then laying-up the sandwich constructions in the flange and web and their internal cover to form the sandwich box beam. Join the inside partitions and lay-up the super flange by them and thus forming the overall box beam made of sandwich construction. This process easily brings the defectiveness that the angles of the beam are easy multi-shell curing to occur fault planes in them. Besides, it is not easy to have an exact dimensions and the roof hard to make plain and smooth, the fiber can not be made tense and tight, and the cover of the roof adhered on the uneven sandwich construction surface, it is both difficult and unsafe to guarantee its quality.

So we have two ways of improvement;

- (a) First stick a layer or more of thick cloth to the outer of the sandwich layer of the box beam (upper the sandwich, down the cloth, mould with pressure), then join it to the open laminated box beam (inner the sandwich, outer the cloth, mould with pressure), later laying-up may be continuously progress based on the moulded layer, which is both effective and simple to operate.
 (b) As to the small size box beams made of sandwich construction or multi-room box

beams, after finishing the open laminate box beam and its sandwich and joining the transverse partitions inside the beam, first make preformed channel laminate to join the flange and the web and make it as part of the super flange, then form the remaining part of the flange on it. If the cross-section size is quite large and the span is quite long, according to the requirements of the structure, the boxes beam made of sandwich construction may be prefabricated in parts and the on-the-spot construction realise its overall structure by making use of bottom model and prefabricated core box to ply up outer covers of the beam continuously. At the joints where the inner sides and the webs of the box beam are reinforced by means of wet joining or where the two ends of the preplaced steel bars in the box are reinforced by means of mechanical connection.

The above improvement may shorten the manufacture cycle and avert the delamination at the turning angle of the box beam and twice of curing forming. At the same time, the evenness of the box beam especially its roof plane, the size of the inner and outer box, the construction of the fiber and the sticking effect on the surface of the sandwich construction are all able to be guaranteed. Therefore, the structural characteristics are not only expected to be promoted but also realise the great progress of in manufacture process and construction technology of the overall structure's forming of the rapid assembly on the spot and of the stage prefabrication of long-span GRP structure in the plant.

References

1. Y. Shuzhen, *A Word For the Development of GRP Bridges, Construction of Bridges*, No. 1, 1990.
2. M. Holmes and D. J. Just, *GRP in Structural Engineering, Applied Science Publishers Ltd.*, 1983.
3. M. Xipeng, *A Study on the GRP Highway Freebeam Bridges*, 1989.
4. C. Lieming, *The Equilibrium Problem of Composite Closed Thin-wall bars, ACTA Material Compositae Sinica*, No. 1, 1984.
5. Harbin Architecture Engineering Institute, *Analysis and Design of GRP Structures*, China Architecture Industry Press, 1981.
6. Chongqing University of Communications, *A Research Report on GRP cabled Bridge*, 1987.
7. F. Guangzhan, *Experimental Analysis of GRP Model Bridge, FRP/Composite*, No. 1. 1990.
8. S. Yunlai, *The Experimental Study of combined Beams of GRP box Beams and Reinforced Concrete Plate, FRP/Composite*, No. 3. 1989.
9. U. Meier, R. Muller and A. Puck, *FRP-Box Beams under Static and Fatigue Loading*, Proceedings of the International Conferenc on Testing Evaluation and Quality Control of Composites Guibdford, Editof Feest Butterworth, 1983.
10. Chongqign University of Communications, *The Eperimental Research Report on the GRP Box Beam Made of Sandwich Construction under Static, Dynamic Loading*, 1992.
11. M. Xipeng *The FRP Highway Freebeam Bridge (I) - The Study on the 1/4 model beam, FRP/composites*, No. 6, 1992.
12. Cristos C. Chamis and PappuL. N. Murthy, *Design Procedures for Fiber Composite Box Beams, Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites* No. 8, 1989.
13. W. Zhuqi, *A Complete Collection of China GRP Industry*, National Defense Industry Press (China), 1991.
14. W. Shunting, *Fiber Reinforced Plastic Process*, Wuhan Industry university Press, 1989.
15. Y. Bing, *A study on GRP Application in the Bridge Structures*, Proceedings of Ninth FRP/CM Annual Conference, (China) 1991.
16. Z. XiXiang, *The Research on Evaluation of Load Carrying Capacity of Damaged Composite Structures*, Journal of Chongqing Communication University, No. 3, 1992.